

Original Research Article

Prevalence of Malaria among COVID-19 Patients accessing Healthcare in Selected Facilities in Rivers State Nigeria

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Abstract

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Nigeria is a malaria endemic country with huge disease burden and lately has suffered the devastating effect of the novel corona viral disease with obvious mortality rate and comorbid conditions. The cross sectional hospital based study, investigated the prevalence of malaria among 400 COVID-19 patients accessing Healthcare in Selected Facilities in Rivers State Nigeria. Ethical approvals were obtained from appropriate bodies and unit heads of laboratories and health facilities in addition to informed and written consent from study participants based on eligibility criteria. The investigation of malaria parasitaemia in this study was relative to the clinical manifestations of various symptoms such as fever, difficulty in breathing, cough/sneezing, headache, loss of smell/taste, running nose and sore throat. Malaria count was performed to semi quantitatively examined accordingly using Chessbrough after thick and thin film smear preparations and Romanoskwy staining technique. Results showed varying degrees (low, moderate and high) of malaria prevalence among COVID-19 study participants in relation to symptoms. The least rate was observed as 3.0% categorized as low in relation to fever while symptom accompanied with difficulty in breathing had the highest prevalence of malaria parasitaemia with high severity (62.5%) among study participants presented with this symptom despite the fact that, fewer number of patients (N=24) experienced this symptom of difficulty in breathing compared to the most common symptom of loss of smell/taste (N= 138), only 19.5% of these patients reported high malaria parasitaemia. Most symptoms reported in this study are common for both malaria parasitaemia infection and COVID-19 therefore, to prevent misdiagnosis and misclassification, differential diagnosis is suggested in addition to integrating malaria test as part of the routine screening among COVID-19 case management for best outcome. The deterred safety prevention and control measures for malaria should be reconsidered especially in malaria endemic regions.

Keywords: COVID-19 Patients, Facilities, Healthcare, Malaria, Nigeria, Rivers State

INTRODUCTION

Malaria infection and COVID-19 have reportedly co-existed in some endemic (World Health Organization, 2020). Malaria infection and COVID-19 have not

extensively proven to be mutually exclusive according to evidence; however, this is argued by some scholars based on some facts (World Health Organization, 2020).

While malaria and COVID-19 might possess similar clinical presentation, common symptoms such as those identified in this study such as fever, difficulty in breathing, cough/sneezing, headache, loss of smell/taste, running nose and sore throat. Also, other symptoms not mentioned here. These similar clinical presentations and symptoms can contribute to diagnostic disparity and misdiagnosis of malaria for COVID-19 and vice versa, particularly when clinician relies mainly on symptoms (Hussein et al., 2020).

Africa particularly Nigeria the area of this study, has been involved in the global fight against malaria using different approaches and intervention strategies such as the roll back malaria and others. Nonetheless, some of these programmes have been affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Hussein and colleagues (Hussein et al., 2020) posit that, COVID-19 disturbs the stability of malaria services such as; the Population Services International and the Global Malaria Community, including seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) and insecticide-treated bed nets (ITNs) distribution. Furthermore, testing and treatment of malaria infection experienced obstruction as a result of the pandemic (Hussein et al., 2020). The region was not hugely affected by COVID-19 pandemic and this is typical for Africa (Hussein et al., 2020). As of 1st August 2020, a total of 17,396,943 COVID-19 confirmed cases and 675,060 deaths have been reported worldwide by the WHO (2020). However, only less than five percent were from Africa. Out of 788,488 confirmed cases shared by WHO (2020) as at 1st August, 2020, Nigeria had 43,151 cases confirmed and 879 deaths. Nigeria suffered combined effect of malaria endemicity and COVID-19 pandemicity WHO (2020). Studies have revealed a protective advantage in malaria endemic region showing low rate of COVID-19 (Hussein et al., 2020). This has remained a controversy as other scholars argued this revealing that people who live in malaria-endemic areas and get infected by SARS-CoV-2 may be at increased risk of severe COVID-19 when status of malaria parasitaemia is ignored (Polrat et al., 2021).

Variation in the prevalence of COVID-19 exists as Africa has shown low rate in transmission. Hussein et al. (2020) put forward that, the variable distribution of the ACE1/D and the ACE2 (C1173T substitution) polymorphisms has been postulated to explain this variable prevalence. The angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), hydroxychloroquine and chloroquine, interferons, and the neutralizing antibodies have been postulated to play roles in the low prevalence of COVID-19 in malaria-endemic countries Hussein et al. (2020).

COVID-19 and malaria parasitaemia co-infection in relation to clinical presentation of symptoms have been reported in several COVID-19 studies including case control and case series studies (Onosakponome and Wogu, 2020; Muhammad et al., 2020; Matangila et al., 2020; Amoo et al., 2020; Mahajan et al., 2021). Matangila et al. (2020) considered similar interest relating

to co-infection and severe clinical presentations of symptoms although, the study failed to explain the exact nature of the corresponding complications. According to Mahajan et al. (2021), most studies focused on prevalence of COVID-19 and co-infection prevalence but few of these studies considered the subject in relation to clinical presentation of symptoms. In 2021 he explained the prevalence of co-infection, but had null report on the signs or symptoms at presentation. Nevertheless, over 80% of the healthcare workers examined in their study were not asymptomatic (Mahajan et al., 2021).

Clinical presentations of patients with COVID-19 co-infection assumed better explained using were case reports and case series (Wilairatana et al., 2021). Wilairatana et al. (2021) in a systematic review reported some among which were 12 cases of co-infection described and seven were case reports and series. These studies considered clinical presentation of symptoms of which one of the studies by Adetola et al. (2020) established that, three out of four cases of co-infection were asymptomatic at presentation; the remaining one case presented with cough. While Mahajan et al., (2021) in a different report posited that, two out of three cases of co-infection were asymptomatic at presentation, except one of the cases that presented influenza-like symptoms. Nevertheless, over 80% of the healthcare workers examined in their study were not asymptomatic. The dearth of data with regards to symptoms of COVID-19 and malaria parasitemia in the area of this study caught the researchers attention in this direction and information obtained will be useful in the clinical management of COVID-19 in malaria endemic region particularly in differential diagnosis as well as in the verification of the postulated protected advantage of malaria in such areas.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

Cross sectional hospital based study adopted descriptive approach as design and, investigated the prevalence of malaria among COVID-19 patients accessing Healthcare in Selected Facilities in Rivers State Nigeria.

Study area/Location

Rivers state was the location for this study. Rivers state is one of the states located in South-South Nigeria and Port Harcourt is the capital of the state. The state is known by the high industrial activities especially rich in oil and gas as well as other petroleum activities. The occupations of the people are farming, fishing however; the explorative

activities of the oil and gas have adversely affected the people and the environment. Two referral and tertiary class healthcare facilities are within the state in addition to secondary healthcare facilities located in the zones and zonal hospitals and general hospitals. The state has a functional primary healthcare management board and primary healthcare centres are found in all the twenty-three local government areas within the state. These have served the people in addition to the selected COVID-19 centres within the state which were the sites used for this study.

Eligibility Criteria

This was strictly based on informed written consent of subjects who obliged to participate in the study. Although no age limit was set, all COVID-19 patients on admission within the selected COVID-19 centres in Rivers state present at the time of study that consented were recruited and the available age and sex became the study framework. All cases of COVID-19 not presently on admission in those selected centres were excluded as well as those present who declined participating in the study.

Sampling and Data Collection

Simple random sampling technique was used to sample subjects after a sample size calculation was performed using Cochran (1977) for descriptive study. Data collection was primary source from participants through blood sample collection/analysis and use of questionnaire in addition to extraction of information from the patients' folders.

Laboratory Procedures

Methodological proceedings strictly adhered to standard clinical laboratory practices from pre analytical to post analytical process upholding ethical mannerism in every bit of the research protocol. Malaria count was performed and semi quantitatively examined accordingly using Cheesbrough (2010) prescribed protocol for thick and thin film smear preparations and Romanosky staining technique.

Main outcome was prevalence of malaria amongst COVID-19 patients. General and symptoms specific prevalence rates were obtained categorized according to parasite density as low, moderate, and high malaria parasitaemia. The investigation of malaria parasitaemia in this study was relative to the clinical manifestations of various symptoms such as fever, difficulty in breathing, cough/sneezing, headache, loss of smell/taste, running nose and sore throat.

Data Collation and Statistical Analysis

Data were collated into excel and statistical analysis performed for descriptive statistics using Statistical Package for Social Science version 25. Frequency, percentage and prevalence rates were obtained.

Ethical Issues

Ethical approvals were obtained from appropriate bodies and unit heads of laboratories and health facilities in addition to informed and written consent from study participants based on eligibility criteria of within the study region and must be within the selected health facilities chosen.

RESULTS

The study investigated the prevalence of malaria among COVID-19 patients accessing Healthcare in selected Facilities in Rivers State Nigeria. The investigation of malaria parasitaemia in this study was relative to the clinical manifestations of various symptoms such as fever, difficulty in breathing, cough/sneezing, headache, loss of smell/taste, running nose and sore throat.

Malaria prevalence among COVID-19 study participants in relation to symptoms as presented on Table 1 shows that 66 had fever among which 08(3.0), 27(40.9), and 29(43.9) demonstrated low, moderate and high malaria parasitemia respectively. Nevertheless, 334 subjects did not develop fever with lesser malaria load as; 146(43.7), 87(26.0), and 28(8.3) for low, moderate, and high malaria parasitaemia among COVID-19 subjects without fever. The symptom of difficulty in breathing was observed by 24 patients with varying malaria parasite density as; 02(8.3) low parasitaemia, 07(29.1) moderate malaria parasitaemia, and 15(62.5) high malaria parasitaemia. Cough/Sneezing symptomatic report showed that 67 reportedly had cough/sneezing while 333 COVID-19 patients were asymptomatic for cough/sneezing. With malaria parasitaemia of 142(42.6), 93(27.9), and 24(7.2) for low, moderate and high parasite.

Headache as a symptom was experienced and reported by 64 persons while 336 had no report of headache. For the subjects with headache, 11(17.1) had low malaria parasitemia, 23(35.9) had moderate malaria parasitemia, while 30(46.8) had high malaria parasitaemia as categorically identified in this study. Loss of smell/taste happened to be the highest number of symptoms observed among COVID-19 patients in this study with 262 of the general study population lacked this symptom of loss of smell/taste however, the absence of loss of smell/taste did not revealed absence of malaria infection hence, 76(29.0) had low class of malaria

Table 1. Malaria prevalence among COVID-19 study participants in relation to symptoms

Symptoms	Number Examined	Number Undetected	Malaria Parasitaemia (%)		
			Low	Moderate	High
Fever					
Yes	66	268	08(3.0)	27(40.9)	29(43.9)
No	334		146(43.7)	87(26.0)	28(8.3)
Difficulty in Breathing					
Yes	24	352	02(8.3)	07(29.1)	15(62.5)
No	376		152(40.4)	107(28.4)	42(11.2)
Cough/Sneezing					
Yes	67	266	12(17.9)	21(31.3)	33(49.2)
No	333		142(42.6)	93(27.9)	24(7.2)
Headache					
Yes	64	272	11(17.1)	23(35.9)	30(46.8)
No	336		143(42.5)	91(27.1)	27(8.0)
Loss of Smell/Taste					
Yes	138	124	78(56.5)	32(23.1)	27(19.5)
No	262		76(29.0)	82(31.2)	30(11.4)
Running Nose					
Yes	34	332	15(44.1)	11(32.3)	06(17.6)
No	366		139(37.1)	103(28.1)	51(13.9)
Sore Throat					
Yes	12	376	07(58.3)	04(33.3)	01(8.3)
No	388		147(37.8)	110(28.3)	56(14.4)

parasitaemia, 103(28.1) reported moderate level of malaria infection while 51(13.9) demonstrated high malaria parasitaemia as observed among COVID-19 patients with no symptom of running nose/taste. For those with loss of smell/taste the following malaria parasitaemia result was observed 78(56.5) for low, 32(23.1) for moderate, and 27(19.5) for high.

Running nose was one of the symptoms reported by 34 participants whereas others -366 had no report of running nose. Malaria parasitaemia for participants with running nose revealed 15(44.1) as low, 11(32.3) as moderate and 06(17.6) as high. Furthermore, participants with null running nose had malaria infection of 139(37.1), 103(28.1), and 51(13.9) for low, moderate and high degrees of malaria parasitaemia in this study.

Sore throat associated symptom was reported by 12 participants while 388 had no sore throat. Based on severity of the malaria infection for those with sore throat, study result showed 07(58.3), 04(33.3), and 01(8.3) for low, moderate and high parasitaemia correspondingly. While participants with no sore throat had malaria parasitaemia of 147(37.8), 110(28.3), and 56(14.4) for low, moderate and high malaria load accordingly.

Symptom accompanied with difficulty in breathing had the highest prevalence of malaria parasitaemia with high severity (62.5%) among study participants presented with this symptom despite the fact that, fewer number of patients (N=24) experienced this symptom compared to the most common symptom of loss of smell/taste (N=138), only 19.5% of these patients reported high malaria parasitaemia. See table 1 for detail.

DISCUSSION

The investigation of malaria parasitaemia in this study was relative to the clinical manifestations of various symptoms such as fever, difficulty in breathing, cough/sneezing, headache, loss of smell/taste, running nose and sore throat. This study established the existence of COVID-19 co-infection with malaria among patients accessing care in some health institution in Rivers State. Several studies have established co-infection of malaria and COVID-19 (Correia et al., 2020; Junaedi et al., 2020; Mahajan et al., 2021; Sardar et al., 2020; Ray et al., 2020). Remarkably, some described these issues of COVID-19 co-infection and malaria with different symptoms as seen in this study, and all of these cases presented with fever and other non-specific symptoms as well as different prevalence rate of malaria parasitaemia (Mahajan et al., 2021).

Mahajan et al. (2021) asserted that patients with co-infection had a shorter duration of viral clearance and slow recovery rate compared to others.

Furthermore, the study observed different symptoms among COVID-19 infected patients with malaria parasitaemia however, some COVID-19 patients were asymptomatic which is in conformity with earlier study that showed that COVID-19 patients on admission were asymptomatic (Amoo et al., 2020). Similarly, other studies reported the presence of symptoms and asymptomatic manifestations in patients (Wilairatana et al., 2021; Matangila et al., 2020).

Amoo et al. (2020) specifically observed that majority

of patients were without symptoms upon admission (52%), whereas the remaining patients had mild diseases (48%), including fever (29%), sore throat (24%), and dry cough (20%) which are comparable to the evidence obtained in this study. Furthermore, a separate study performed in 2020 by Matangila et al. (2020) supported that, the majority of the clinical symptoms observed in their study among COVID-19 patients upon admission were synonymous with the observations reported in this study, although with varying degrees and symptoms such as; fever, cough, fatigue, and shortness of breath were reported. The rates in this study is not same with Matangila et al. (2020) for symptom like fever (58%), which is higher than the report obtained in this study for fever (16.5%). The rate of symptomatic fever observed in this study is lower compared to other studies even from same region like the study by Onosakponome and Wogu (2020) which reported that most of the patients with co-infection had fever (79.7%) upon presentation while a lower rate of 16.5% was reported in this study. Onosakponome and Wogu, (2020) reported cases of symptomatic presentation among co-morbid COVID-19 patients in their study like coughs, difficulty breathing, headaches, sore throats, and runny noses. Likewise, these symptoms were identified and reported in this study nonetheless, little discrepancy exists in the prevalence rates of these symptoms between this current study and Onosakponome and Wogu (2020).

Also, Matangila et al. (2020) in a study as well reported that, some symptoms in COVID-19 including fever (64%), dry cough (29%), myalgia (27%), and sore throat (24%). Notably, these rates slightly differed from the rates obtained in this study which recorded loss of smell/taste (34.5%) as the most common symptom reported while sore throat was the lowest rate (3.0%).

Previous studies reported on the clinical manifestation of symptoms among COVID-19 patients demonstrating likely co-infection at the initial presentation (Onosakponome and Wogu, 2020; Muhammad et al., 2020; Matangila et al., 2020; Amoo et al., 2020; Mahajan et al., 2021). This study differ from Amoo et al. (2020) study which reported that all patients with co-infection in their study were asymptomatic whereas in this study, not all cases of co-infection were without at least a form of clinical presentation of symptoms. This could be due to the fact that the region experienced low testing coverage due to scarcity of testing materials and a policy that guided testing as at that time was based on clinical presentation of any of the symptoms unless otherwise. Additionally, clinical presentations of patients with COVID-19 co-infection were also reported in earlier studies like (Wilairatana et al., 2021; Adetola et al., 2020). While Matangila et al. (2020) in a different report posited combination of symptomatic and asymptomatic presentation although majority presented symptoms.

Correia et al. (2020) was in agreement with this study while Ray et al. (2020) had no variation in finding

establishing symptomatic presentation in malaria parasitaemia and COVID-19 co-infection. In the same way, Junaedi et al. (2020) demonstrated similar observation confirming presence of different symptoms in malaria co-infection with COVID-19 among study participants.

Wilairatana et al. (2021) in a general review overview reported that, out of all 12 cases of co-infection, 41.7% were asymptomatic, while the rest (58.3%) presented with fever and non-specific signs or symptoms as recorded in this study however, certain specific detailed signs and symptoms were not captured in this study such as chills, diarrhea, malaise, diaphoresis, occasional dry cough, vomiting, abdominal pain, jaundice, and progressive exertional breathlessness.

COVID-19 and malaria parasitaemia in relation to symptoms as demonstrated in this study is backed up with earlier studies which established co-infection with different severities of malaria parasitaemia classified as low, moderate and high similar to this study outcome such as Onosakponome and Wogu, (2020) reported that 19.3%, 27.7%, and 53% of cases of co-infection involved high, moderate, and low levels of parasitemia, in that order. Matangila et al. (2020) similarly observed of COVID-19 and malaria coinfection with a parasite density of 16,900/ μ L.

Other studies confirmed cases of malaria parasitemia among patients with coinfection. Correia et al. (2020) revealed a parasite load of 83,520 parasites/ μ L (3.1% parasitemia), whereas Junaedi et al. (2020) reported slightly higher value of 119,902 parasites/ μ L. In addition, Sardar et al. (2020) showed a rate of 1.2% parasitemia in a study. These ample evidences which support this study are indications of COVID-19 coinfection with malaria especially in malaria endemic region with different prevalence rates and clinical manifestations.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Malaria parasitaemia and co-infection with COVID-19 was established in this study in relation to symptoms such as fever, difficulty in breathing, cough/sneezing, headache, loss of smell/taste, running nose and sore throat. Remarkably, the study reported different degrees and severities of malaria parasitemia from low, moderate to high. The symptoms were not dependent on the malaria load and vice versa. The impact of COVID-19 is huge and co-infection with malaria poses more complications although this is subject to verification as some studies have suggested a protective advantage hence, this study suggest a further study of the underlying mechanisms to this regards.

Additionally, the study is limited in that, the identified symptoms were not traced to a specific disease outcome in essence, malaria alone or COVID-19 alone rather observation was on a holistic view therefore, differential

diagnosis is suggested to clarify the symptoms and understand the specific infections traceable to all.

Malaria parasitemia should be considered in the management and treatment of COVID-19 and COVID-19 should be looked at whenever malaria parasite infection is treated because all 400 study participants were both positive to malaria and COVID-19. Although, with varying symptoms and grades of malaria parasite loads. This consideration is proposed for malaria endemic region. Hence, all COVID-19 safety measures and measures for malaria prevention and control programmes should be recalled and practiced.

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